

Synthesis of some 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-yl Chalcones and related Iso-oxazoles as Potential Fungicides

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Several 3-(7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-yl)-5-arylisooxazoles were synthesised by condensing hydroxylamine hydrochloride with 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-yl chalcones. The chalcones were prepared through the condensation reaction between 8-acetyl-7-hydroxycoumarin and aromatic aldehydes. All the compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity on *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* and some of them revealed notable activity.

THE coumarin derivatives have been used extensively in designing various pesticidal agents including some well-known rodenticides, insecticides and also fungicides¹. The chalcones by virtue of incorporating -CH=CH-CO- grouping appear to be potential chemical entity for designing useful pesticidal agents because this feature is also present in many antibiotics, pyrethroids and chemical compounds of heartwood of several plants² resistant to attack by insects and fungi, and as such it is apparently implicated in their biological manifestations. Likewise, the pesticidal potentiality of iso-oxazole derivatives is well documented³.

In view of these records, it was anticipated that incorporation of chalcone feature in coumarins and joining of coumarin and iso-oxazole heterocycles together would furnish compounds of enhanced fungicidal properties, hence the synthesis and bioassay of title compounds was undertaken.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was prepared⁴ by condensation of ethyl acetoacetate and resorcinol. Acetylation of phenolic function of coumarin⁴ with acetic anhydride furnished 7-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin (1), which upon Fries rearrangement⁵ gave 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2). Compound 2 on condensation⁶ with aromatic aldehydes furnished the chalcones (3). On refluxing⁷ 3 with hydroxylamine hydrochloride gave the desired compound 4 was obtained (Scheme 1).

All the compounds (3 and 4) were screened for their antifungal activity by agar growth technique on *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at three concentrations (1000, 100 and 10 ppm). Carbendazim was also tested for comparison purpose (Table 1). The number of replication in each case was three.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrometer and the nmr

Scheme 1

spectra (DMSO-d₆) on EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer.

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2): A mixture of 7-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin (0.1 mol) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.15 mol) was heated in an oil-bath at 160–65° for 3 h. After cooling the mass was decomposed with ice-HCl and the product was taken into ether. It was washed well with water and dried. Removal of ether gave the product which was crystallised twice with aqueous ethanol, m.p. 172–75°, (lit.⁸ 168°).

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-yl chalcones (3): A mixture of 2 (0.02 mol, 1.8 g) and 4-methylbenzaldehyde (0.02 mol, 1.0 g) was dissolved in hot methanol (15 ml). To it a 40% solution of methanolic KOH (10 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 10 min and kept overnight at room temperature. It was then diluted five times with water and extracted with ether. The ether layer was removed and the aqueous layer acidified with dilute HCl. It was again extracted with ether and dried. Removal of ether gave the

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Sl. no.	R	M.p °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Average % Inhibition after 96 h					
					<i>H. oryzae</i>			<i>A. niger</i>		
					1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
3a	4-OH ₂	140	77	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄	60.2	40.4	26.3	55.2	38.4	22.9
3b	3-Nitro	45	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₃	80.6	72.4	69.3	70.2	50.2	42.8
3c	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -3-OCH ₃	135	77	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₅	82.4	73.1	70.0	69.4	48.4	42.0
3d	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -n-3-OCH ₃	125	71	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₅	59.9	40.0	26.2	52.5	36.3	20.2
3e	4-(N(CH ₃) ₂)	60	88	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ NO ₄	54.4	38.6	24.2	50.2	30.0	16.4
3f	2-OH-3,5-(Br ₂)	165	84	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Br ₂ O ₅	61.2	41.0	27.2	62.4	36.0	18.4
3g	2-OH-5-OH ₂	100	87	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅	57.3	39.4	25.8	53.3	36.1	19.2
3h	4-Cl	140	78	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClO ₄	81.1	72.9	69.8	67.4	44.0	30.4
4a	4-OH ₂	120	66	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ NO ₄	58.8	38.6	22.6	50.2	32.0	20.5
4b	3-NO ₂	35	83	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₅	60.4	40.7	27.2	58.4	35.5	20.7
4c	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -3-OCH ₃	105	62.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₅	61.1	41.0	27.3	52.5	35.5	19.6
4d	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -n-3-OCH ₃	110	66	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₅	55.3	36.0	22.4	50.4	31.8	19.3
4e	4-(N(CH ₃) ₂)	45	71	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅	51.1	32.4	20.1	48.4	28.3	16.2
4f	2-OH-3,5-(Br ₂)	140	83	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Br ₂ NO ₅	60.2	40.1	26.3	54.4	36.2	22.4
4g	2-OH-5-OH ₂	80	55.5	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ NO ₅	55.5	38.3	24.3	51.1	32.1	16.3
4h	4-Cl	125	85	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClNO ₄	80.0	70.1	67.3	77.3	66.4	60.2
	Carbendazim				90.2	80.6	78.4	90.0	81.0	77.8

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

desired chalcone (3a; 2.0 g, 77%), m.p. 140° (Found: C, 74.58; H, 5.51. C₂₀H₁₆O₄ requires: C, 75.00; H, 5.00%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2950 (OH chelation), 1680 (C=O, α,β -unsaturated), 1270 (C-O-C) and 1560 cm⁻¹ (coumarin ring).

Similarly, other chalcones were prepared (Table 1).

3-(7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-yl)-5-aryliso-oxazoles (4): To a mixture of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.015 mol, 1.2 g/10 ml ethanol) and sodium acetate (0.03 mol, 1.6 g/10 ml hot acetic acid) was added, a solution of 4-methyl-(4'-methyl-7'-hydroxycoumarin-8-yl)chalcone (0.01 mol, 1.48 g) dissolved in ethanol (15 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h and cooled. It was then diluted with water (100 ml) and neutralised with dilute NaOH. The product separating after acidification with dilute HCl was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (4a; 1.0 g, 66%), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 72.26; H, 5.12; N, 4.53. C₂₀H₁₆NO₄ requires: C, 72.07; H, 4.50; N, 4.20%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2950 (OH chelation), 1680 (C=O, α,β -unsaturated), 1180 (C-O-C), 1600 (aromatic ring), 1620 (C=N) and 1560 cm⁻¹ (coumarin ring); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.8 (6H, 2CH₃), 5.9 (2H, olefinic), 7.3 (1H, OH) and 7.7–8.1 (6H, ArH).

Similarly, other iso-oxazoles were prepared (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

A perusal of fungitoxicity data (Table 1) reveals that all the compounds are fairly toxic to both the species of fungi. But their activity decreases considerably with dilution. The activity of coumarinyl chalcones is more on both the fungi than coumarinyl iso-oxazoles. Probably it is due to the presence of toxophoric α,β -unsaturated ketonic function in the chalcones.

Compounds 3b, 3c and 4h have activities quite comparable with commercial fungicide carbendazim. Their activities are due to the presence of polar substitute like OC₂H₅, NO₂ and Cl. Further investigation of these compounds on a wider range of fungi and dilution is desirable.

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References

1. K. MAIKAWA and H. YOSHIKAWA, *Adv. Pestic. Sci. Plenary Sect. Symp. Pap. Int. Congr. Pestic. Chem.*, 1978, 4, 104; S. NAKAJIMA, S. SUGIYAMA and M. SUTO, *Org. Prep. Proceed. Int.*, 1979, 11, 77; S. GIRI and Y. SINGH, *Bokin Bobat*, 1978, 6, 340.
2. P. L. SAWHNEY and T. R. SESHADRI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. Sect. B*, 1954, 13, 5.
3. K. TOMITA, H. OKA and Y. KONDO, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, 78, 25556; D. DAVENPORT, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, 88, 121155; G. HENBACH and B. SACHSE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 86, 106569; S. A. PHILAGRO, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 90, 137797; H. TSUJI, K. TOMITA, S. YAMAMOTO, T. HONMA and Y. TAKAH, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 86, 5441; K. TOMITA, T. MURAKAMI, T. HONMA and Y. YAMAZAKI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 83, 48805; K. TOMITA, H. OKO, T. MURAKAMI, H. TSUJI and K. MATSUMOTO, *San'kyo Kenkyusho Nempo*, 1978, 30, 193; H. TSUJI, K. TOMITA, S. YAMAMOTO, J. HONMA and Y. TAKAH, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 85, 192702; N. SAMPREI, K. TOMITA, H. TSUJI, T. YAMJ, H. OKA and T. YAMAMOTO, *San'kyo Kenkyusho Nempo*, 1970, 22, 221.
4. P. G. MANN and B. O. SAUNDERS, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th. ed., 1970, pp. 305, 108.
5. A. B. SRN and S. S. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 29, 407.
6. N. M. SHAH and S. R. PARIKH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36, 726.
7. M. A. ELKASABY and M. A. I. SALEM, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 571.
8. R. D. DRSAI and A. HAMID, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1938, 32, 1254.